

Porous Polymer-Based Frictional Area-Separating Layer Jamming Mechanism(FASLJM) for Tunable Stiffness Profiles

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Abstract—Layer jamming mechanisms (LJMs) are widely used as pneumatic variable-stiffness methods but often suffer from unintended residual stiffness under external normal loading and during pressure release, which degrades real-time stiffness control. In this work, we propose a Frictional Area-Separating Layer Jamming Mechanism (FASLJM) that inserts a porous polymer layer to mechanically separate high-friction interfaces in the low-pressure regime while preserving high packing density. The resulting stiffness profile maintains low stiffness below a critical pressure and increases abruptly beyond it. A two-regime analytical model is developed and experimentally validated using friction coefficients identified from single-material surface LJMs. By systematically varying key design parameters, experiments confirm that the stiffness profile can be tuned and closely follows the model predictions. Compared with a conventional high-friction LJM, the proposed FASLJM exhibited up to more than twofold lower stiffness under an external load of 500 g, as well as 2.6 times lower residual torque at low angular velocity actuation (0.04 rad/s) and 2.1 times lower residual torque at high angular velocity actuation (0.2 rad/s) during rapid vacuum pressure exhaust from a high-pressure state.

Index Terms—Layer Jamming Mechanism, Variable Stiffness, Passive Actuator, Porous Polymer, Tunable Stiffness Profile

I. INTRODUCTION

Unlike traditional robots composed of rigid bodies, soft robots have been actively studied in various application fields, particularly in the human robot interaction field, due to their compliant characteristics. However, this low stiffness of soft robots creates a trade-off in terms of precise control and strong force transmission, and in this context, what began to be studied is the variable stiffness method (VSM) of soft robots. Currently, various types of VSMs using pneumatic, thermal [1]–[4], and magnetic/electric [5]–[7] stimuli are being studied.

In pneumatic-based VSM, approaches using positive pressure [8], [9] also exist, but jamming mechanism using negative pressure has received much attention due to reasons such as stability and low hysteresis. The jamming mechanism tunes stiffness in a manner such that, when vacuum pressure is applied inside a pneumatic pouch with structures such as particle [10]–[12], fiber [13]–[15], layer [16]–[22], and other structures [23] inserted inside, the pressure difference increases the normal force between the structures and the friction force increases together.

Among them, the approach that has been most actively studied based on a high contact area is the Layer Jamming Mechanism (LJM). Basically, the stiffness of LJM is proportional to the number of layers, the pressure difference, the

friction coefficient, and the area of the layers. Therefore, it shows a linear increase in stiffness with pressure, and for miniaturization of the actuator and performance enhancement, the stiffness increase rate with respect to pressure increases. However, pneumatic actuators, particularly negative-pressure-based actuators that have the advantage of parallel actuation of multiple actuators, have bulky and complex backend systems, and thus a difference occurs between the pressure input at the regulator and the pressure output at the end-effector. In particular, when venting from a high vacuum pressure, it takes a long time for the pressure inside the actuator to return to the atmospheric pressure level due to the low flow conductance of the backend system, and this can be a problem in that unintended stiffness is left, especially in real-time adjustment of actuator stiffness through continuous pressure control.

This issue occurs in the same manner even when external loads are applied from outside the actuator. When LJM is attached to and used with another active actuator, or used as a component of a wearable robot, the actuator is more likely to be exposed to external loads, and thus external loads in the direction normal to the layers play the same role as pressure and result in stiffness different from the control input. In addition, as surfaces with higher friction coefficients are used, the jamming status is not completely released even when the internal pressure of the actuator becomes atmospheric pressure, and thus this residual stiffness problem needs to be resolved.

Therefore, in this study, a Frictional Area-Separating Layer Jamming Mechanism (FASLJM) was developed by inserting a porous polymer inside the layers, thereby maintaining high packing density while mechanically preventing contact of high-friction layers in the low-pressure region. With this actuator, low stiffness is maintained even under external loading applied in the direction normal to the layer or under drastic vacuum pressure control, and after the critical pressure, stiffness increases abruptly, thereby showing that unintended stiffness, which has been a chronic problem of LJM from a control perspective, can be meaningfully removed. In addition, it was shown that the fabricated FASLJM follows the modeled stiffness profile well, and in conclusion, it was shown that the stiffness profile of LJM can be tuned to be suitable for future control and design purposes.

Fig. 1. Design of the FASLJM. (a) Appearance of the FASLJM before insertion into the pneumatic pouch, (b) surface configuration of a single layer, and (c) sectional view of the layer. The high-friction surface is attached with 100-grit sandpaper, and a low-stiffness polymer layer is attached beneath the low-friction layer, protruding above the surrounding surface.

II. DESIGN & FABRICATION

A. FASLJM: Design and Mechanism

FASLJM consists of a stacked multi-layer structure, as shown in Fig.1a, where each layer is fixed at both ends and at the center. At the central region, layers from both sides intersect and are stacked. When the internal pressure of the actuator is reduced through the outer pouch, the normal force at the interfacial regions between layers increases, accompanied by an increase in friction. The central fixation follows the same approach as in previous studies [16], [24], where soft pins are connected using thread, allowing the pins to be squeezed together without occupying internal volume even under compression.

As illustrated in Fig.1b and c, each layer is composed of a high-frictional surface and a low-frictional surface. A low-stiffness polymer layer is attached beneath the annular low-frictional surface, enabling downward deformation under increasing vacuum pressure. This deformation induces contact between the lower surface of the upper layer and the high-frictional surface, resulting in a rapid increase in stiffness.

B. Fabrication of Porous Polymer Layer

The porous polymer was selected to use a material that maintains low stiffness and exhibits relatively shape-independent contraction characteristics, even in situations where the surrounding space is constrained, due to its low Poisson's ratio. To fabricate this material, a sugar-based

Fig. 2. Fabrication process of the porous polymer layer. Part A and Part B of each polymer and sugar were mixed at a mass ratio of 1:1:4 and degassed in a vacuum chamber, followed by molding into a mold and curing in an oven at 50 °C for 2 hours. After demolding, the sugar was dissolved in hot water, and the specimen was finally dried in an oven at 50 °C for 15 minutes to complete fabrication.

method was employed, as shown in Fig.2, which was demonstrated in previous studies [25] to enable the fabrication of porous polymers at low cost without affecting the material properties.

For the fabrication of the target materials, two polymers ((Ecoflex™ 00-30, Smooth-On, Inc.), (Dragon Skin™ 30, Smooth-On, Inc.)) were each mixed by weight in a 1:1:4 ratio of Part A, Part B, and sugar, followed by degassing in a vacuum chamber. The mixture was then poured into a mold sprayed with a Release Agent (Ease Release™ 200, Smooth-On, Inc.). The samples were subsequently cured in an incubator at 50 °C for 2 hours, demolded, and then immersed in hot water to dissolve and remove the sugar. Finally, the samples were dried in an incubator at 50 °C for 15 minutes.

C. Fabrication of FASLJM

The layer base, low-stiffness layer, and soft pins of the FASLJM were fabricated from PLA material using an FDM printer (X1-Carbon, Bambu Lab). Sil-Poxy was used to bond both the porous polymer layer to the layer base and the porous polymer to the low-stiffness layer. Subsequently, 100-grit sandpaper, laser-cut to match the design of the high-friction surface, was attached to the layer base, and as described previously, four layers were assembled using thread and soft pins.

The topmost layer, which is used only on its lower surface, consists solely of PLA without the attachment of sandpaper or polymer. The second layer from the bottom was designed, as shown in Fig.3, to match the total height of the stacked layers so that no clearance occurs when the outer pouch contracts. The fabricated FASLJM was then placed inside a pouch prepared by bonding fabric using an impulse heater, and completed by puncturing the pouch and attaching a pneumatic line connector (Threaded Connector, MISUMI) through a pre-designed hole. The overall design parameters of the baseline FASLJM were determined as listed in table.I.

Fig. 3. Fabrication of FASLJM: (a) Overall configuration of the FASLJM. The topmost layer, for which only the bottom surface is involved in actuation, consists of a PLA flat plate, and the second layer from the bottom includes an additional plate-shaped structure on its lower side to fill the empty space and reduce clearance during contraction. Holes are provided at the center and at both ends of each layer for soft pin and thread connections, as well as a hole for connecting the pneumatic line connector. (b, c) Design parameters for the layer configuration. The parameter D is defined as $2 \cdot r$, with $r_2 = r - w/2$ and $r_3 = r + w/2$.

TABLE I
DESIGN PARAMETERS OF THE BASELINE FASLJM

Parameter	Symbol	Value [mm]
Outer Radius	R	15
Inner Hole Radius	r_1	1.5
Low Friction Layer Radius	r	10
Low Friction Layer Width	w	4
Low Friction Layer Thickness	t	1.4
Polymer Layer Thickness	t_{polymer}	2.0
Layer Thickness	t_{layer}	2.9
Layer Bottom Thickness	t_{bottom}	0.5
Number of Layers	N	3

III. MODELING

A. Modeling of Single-Material Surface LJM

To measure the single friction coefficient of each surface used in the FASLJM, an LJM model composed of a single material over the entire surface was constructed. Under this configuration, the quasi-equilibrium torque balance equation (1) induced by the external force applied through the jig can be expressed as shown below. Accordingly, the maximum static friction coefficient can be obtained from the maximum static friction force as a function of pressure. According to the relationship between the pressure ΔP and $(F_{ex})_{\text{static,max}}$ expressed in Equation (2), the experimental data were linearly fitted, and the constant value that minimizes the least-squares error was adopted as the maximum static friction coefficient μ respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} (F_{ex})_{\text{static,max}} \cdot R_{\text{jig}} &= N \cdot \int d\tau & (1) \\ &= N \cdot \int \mu n x dA \\ &= \frac{2}{3} N \pi \mu \Delta P (R^3 - r_1^3) \end{aligned}$$

$$(F_{ex})_{\text{static,max}} = \frac{2\pi N (R^3 - r_1^3) \mu \Delta P}{3R_{\text{jig}}} \quad (2)$$

B. Modeling of FASLJM

Fig. 4. Free-body diagrams of a single layer under external pressure. (a) When the pressure difference is lower than the critical pressure, the external force acts only on the low-friction layer; therefore, a normal stress proportional to the contact area and the pressure difference is applied. (b) When the pressure difference exceeds the critical pressure, the displacement of the low-friction layer becomes constrained, resulting in a constant normal stress of $n_{1,\text{max}}$ in this region, while the remaining force is uniformly applied as n_2 over the high-friction layer.

In the case of the FASLJM, the external force induced by the pressure difference and the normal stresses acting on each surface can be expressed as shown in Fig. 4. It is assumed that the normal stress acting over the same area is identical, and that deformation induced by the applied stress occurs only in the polymer layer beneath the low-friction layer, while all other components are assumed to be rigid and undergo no deformation. When the pressure is lower than the critical pressure, the normal stress generated in the high-friction area becomes zero. Conversely, when the pressure exceeds the critical pressure, the normal stress generated in the low-friction area remains constant at the value of $\frac{A}{A_1} P_{\text{critical}}$, which corresponds to the normal stress at the critical pressure.

$$n_1 = \begin{cases} \frac{A}{A_1} \cdot \Delta P & (0 \leq \Delta P \leq P_{\text{critical}}) \\ n_{1,\text{max}} = \frac{A}{A_1} \cdot P_{\text{critical}} & (\Delta P \geq P_{\text{critical}}) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$n_2 = \begin{cases} 0 & (0 \leq \Delta P \leq P_{\text{critical}}) \\ \frac{A}{A_2} \cdot [\Delta P - P_{\text{critical}}] & (\Delta P \geq P_{\text{critical}}) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Based on the normal stresses defined as equations (3) and (4), the torque equilibrium relations for the two pressure regimes are expressed as equations (5) and (6), respectively, as follows.

1) *Subcritical pressure regime:*

$$\begin{aligned} (F_{ex})_{static,max} &= \frac{N}{R_{jig}} \cdot \int d\tau \\ &= \frac{N}{R_{jig}} \cdot \int \mu_1 n_1 x dA \\ &= \frac{2N\pi\mu_1 A}{3R_{jig}A_1} \Delta P (r_3^3 - r_2^3) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

2) *Supercritical pressure regime:*

$$\begin{aligned} (F_{ex})_{static,max} &= \frac{N}{R_{jig}} \int d\tau \\ &= \frac{N}{R_{jig}} \cdot \left[\int \mu_1 n_1 x dA + \int \mu_2 n_2 x dA \right] \\ &= \frac{2N\pi A}{3R_{jig}} \left[\frac{\mu_1 P_{critical}}{A_1} (r_3^2 - r_2^2) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\mu_2 (\Delta P - P_{critical})}{A_2} (R^3 + r_2^3 - r_3^3 - r_1^3) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

IV. EVALUATION

A. Compressive Test of Porous Polymer

Fig. 5. Compressive Test of Porous Polymer. Cylindrical specimens of pristine and porous versions fabricated using Ecoflex™ 00-30 and Dragon Skin™ 30 were prepared, and experiments were conducted in (a) a free-space case in which the lateral surface of the specimen was unconstrained and (b) a constrained case in which the lateral surface was fully confined.

To verify the material properties of the porous polymer fabricated in Section.II-B, compressive stress–strain experiments were conducted. The materials tested consisted of four types in total: pristine and porous versions of two polymers ((Ecoflex™ 00-30, Smooth-On, Inc.), (Dragon Skin™ 30, Smooth-On, Inc.)). Each specimen was fabricated in a cylindrical shape with a diameter of 30 mm and a thickness of 5 mm.

As shown in Fig.5, the experiments were performed using a Compression Testing Machine(ASM-1000, DIGITECH) equipped with an end tip having a circular cross section with a diameter of 30 mm to compress the specimen. Two types of test conditions were considered: a free-space case and a constrained case. For the free-space case, the specimen was placed on a flat PLA plate fabricated using an FDM printer, and the experiment was conducted in this configuration. For the constrained case, a PLA plate was fabricated in the same manner, but with a cavity of the same shape as the specimen, and the specimen was placed inside the cavity during testing. For each condition, four specimens were prepared under identical conditions and each was tested once. The test was terminated when the compressive strain exceeded 0.6 or when the stress exceeded 100 kPa.

The results of the compression experiments are shown in Fig.6. All specimens exhibited higher stiffness in the constrained case than in the free-space case, with specimens based on Ecoflex™ 00-30 showing relatively larger differences. In particular, for the porous Ecoflex™ 00-30 model, low stiffness was maintained in the constrained condition at low strain ranges due to the characteristics of porosity, followed by a rapid increase in stiffness at higher strain ranges. In contrast, models based on Dragon Skin™ 30, which has inherently higher stiffness, showed no significant difference in behavior between the free-space and constrained cases, and the experimental data also exhibited lower variability compared to Ecoflex™ 00-30. Based on these observations, the porous Dragon Skin™ 30 model was considered to better reflect shape-independent compressive characteristics observed in free space even under constrained conditions, and, additionally, to show well-distinguished strain variations with pressure changes even in low-pressure regimes. For these reasons, it was selected as the material for the FASLJM. The compressive characteristic curve of porous Dragon Skin™ 30 shown in Fig.6 was subsequently used to determine the critical pressure of the FASLJM.

B. Single-Material Surface LJM Experiments for Friction Coefficient Measurement

To measure the friction coefficients of each surface used in the experiments based on the relationship of the single material surface LJM modeled in Section.III-A, the following experiment was conducted. One LJM was configured with PLA on both the upper and lower surfaces, while another LJM consisted of one surface made of 100-grit sandpaper and the other surface made of PLA. All other design parameters adopted the same structure as the baseline FASLJM design parameters defined in TableI.

A wire was connected to the Compression Testing Machine used in Section.IV-A, and the LJM was installed as shown in Fig.7a and mounted on a jig ($R_{jig} = 25mm$) that induces bending. On the backend, a vacuum pump (Rocker 300, ROCKER) was connected to a vacuum pressure regulator (ITV2091-012CL5, SMC), and the actuator was connected through a 2.6 m long 6×4 mm air tube. The signal voltage applied to the vacuum pressure regulator was supplied using a DC power supply (RDP-305AU, GEST). The experimental vacuum pressures were 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 kPa, and for each pressure, bending experiments from 0° to 30° were performed three times. Afterward, the maximum static friction points at which slipping occurred were manually marked on each experimental curve.

The angle–torque experimental results are shown in Fig.8a, b and the pressure–slipping torque data are shown in Fig.7b. Based on the data plotted in the pressure–slipping torque plane, linear fitting was performed using the polyfit function in MATLAB. The fitted relationships for the PLA–PLA LJM and the PLA–sandpaper LJM were τ [N · m] = $0.0134 \cdot P$ [kPa] – 0.0087 and τ [N · m] = $0.0366 \cdot P$ [kPa] + 0.0409, respectively. According to Eq.2, the friction coefficients of each model were set to $\mu_1 = 1.696$ and $\mu_2 = 0.636$.

Fig. 6. Results of the compressive tests of polymer specimens. (a) Experimental results for specimens fabricated based on Ecoflex™ 00-30, (b) experimental results for specimens fabricated based on Dragon Skin™ 30, and (c) summarized results for the constrained cases. Each experiment was conducted once for four specimens, and the results are presented based on the averaged values. The tests were terminated when the compressive strain exceeded 0.6 or the compressive stress exceeded 100 kPa.

Fig. 7. Experimental setup and results of the bending stiffness test. (a) The experimental setup consists of a compression testing machine, vacuum pump, vacuum pressure regulator, DC power supply, and a testing jig, and the regulator and the actuator are connected by a 2.6 m long 6 × 4 mm air tube. (b) Slipping torque–pressure plots corresponding to the experimental results shown in Fig.8(a–c). The experimental results of the PLA–PLA and PLA–Sandpaper Single Material Surface LJMs were fitted to linear functions using the MATLAB polyfit function, and the fitted values were substituted into the model and expressed as the model curves of the FASLJM.

C. FASLJM Stiffness Profile Tuning Experiments Based on Design Parameters

Based on the FASLJM designed with the parameters listed in Table.I, bending tests were conducted in the same manner as described in Section.IV-B. In this section, an additional experiment at a vacuum pressure of 5 kPa was performed in order to further measure the stiffness of the actuator in a low-pressure state. The experimental results are shown in Fig.8d, e, f and g. The modeling was carried out based on μ_1 and μ_2 determined in Section.IV-B, and the values of τ [N · m]/P [kPa] before and after the critical pressure were calculated as 0.0135 and 0.0365, respectively. The critical pressure was calculated as 11.56 kPa by scaling proportionally with the area ratio, using the pressure corresponding to the critical strain of 0.5 in Fig.6c as the reference. The resulting modeling curves and the experimental data are shown in Fig.9.

The next set of experiments was performed on two FASLJM models in which the value of D was set to 17.5 and 15, respectively, based on the baseline FASLJM design, and the angle–torque curves obtained from these experiments are shown in Fig. 8c, f, and g. For these designs, although the

critical strain of the porous polymer layer is the same, the area ratios differ, resulting in different critical pressures of 10.11 kPa and 8.67 kPa, respectively. Accordingly, based on equation.(5), (6), the values of τ [N · m]/P [kPa] before and after the critical pressure also differ. The model curves for the pressure–slipping torque of each actuator and the corresponding experimental data are shown in Fig. 9a.

The final experiment in this section investigated actuators in which the thickness of the low-friction layer was decreased and increased by 0.1 mm from the original value of 1.4 mm, thereby changing the critical strain value. Since the surface design is identical, the values of τ [N · m]/P [kPa] remain the same, but because the critical strain values are 0.45 and 0.55, respectively, the critical pressures in the model change to 9.63 kPa and 14.20 kPa. The angle–torque data for this experiment are shown in Fig. 8c, d, and e, and the pressure–slipping torque data together with the model curves are shown in Fig. 9b. From the experimental results, it can be confirmed that as the thickness of the low-friction layer decreases, the transition from the subcritical pressure regime to the supercritical pressure regime occurs earlier, as expected, and follows the model curves more closely.

Possible sources of error in the bending tests of the FASLJM include pressure-independent terms arising from elongation of the wire, the stiffness of the outer pouch, and friction generated during rotation of the jig, as well as errors introduced during fabrication. In particular, variations in thickness and porosity that occur during the fabrication of the porous polymer layer, differences arising because Sil-Poxy used in the fabrication process occupies and cures within the polymer—leading to discrepancies compared to the compressive properties of the specimen—and deviations between the CAD design values and the printed geometry during fabrication of the low-friction layer using an FDM printer (X1-Carbon, Bambu Lab) can all contribute to experimental error. Finally, from an actuation perspective, the use of soft pins can result in imperfect alignment and twisting of the centers of each layer during operation of the FASLJM, and discrepancies between the model and the experimental behavior arising from this misalignment are also considered to be a significant source of error.

Fig. 8. Results of the bending stiffness test: (a) PLA–PLA Single Material Surface LJM, (b) PLA–Sandpaper Single Material Surface LJM, (c) baseline FASLJM with D20 and t1.3, (d) FASLJM with t1.4, (e) FASLJM with t1.5, (f) FASLJM with D15, and (g) FASLJM with D17.5. For each pressure condition, three trials were conducted, and the slipping points from static to kinetic motion were manually marked.

Fig. 9. Experimental results of Section IV-C. (a) Slipping torque–pressure plots of FASLJMs fabricated by varying the design parameter D of the low-friction layer to 20 mm, 17.5 mm, and 15 mm, corresponding to the experimental results shown in Fig. 8c, f and g. (b) Slipping torque–pressure plots of FASLJMs fabricated by varying the design parameter t of the low-friction layer to 1.3 mm, 1.4 mm, and 1.5 mm, corresponding to the experimental results shown in Fig. 8c, d and e.

D. Demonstration of Stiffness Variation Under External Loading

In this section, experiments were conducted to evaluate the magnitude of torque generated when the external load is applied in the direction normal to the layers. The actuators used in the experiments were the baseline FASLJM and a PLA–sandpaper single-material surface LJM. In the absence of applied vacuum pressure, a 500 g weight was placed on the top of the actuator as shown in Fig. 10a, and bending tests were performed in the same manner as in the previous experiments.

The experimental results are shown in Fig. 10b. While the single-material surface LJM exhibited an increase in torque exceeding $0.1 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$, the FASLJM maintained a lower torque level of approximately $0.05 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$. Considering that conventional LJMs typically use low-stiffness fabric or polymer ma-

Fig. 10. Experimental procedure and results of Section IV-D. (a) The experiment was conducted by applying an external load in the direction normal to the actuator layers by placing a 500 g weight along the guide prepared on the testing jig. (b) Torque profiles obtained while actuating the baseline FASLJM (t1.3, D20) and the PLA–Sandpaper Single Material Surface LJM from 0° to 30° . Three trials were conducted for each case, and the ranges and mean values of the results are shown in the plot.

terials as pouches to allow contraction under vacuum pressure, and that attaching stiff materials externally is not feasible in order to maintain compliant behavior, it can be inferred that a filtering function such as that provided by the FASLJM is necessary for LJM operation that is more independent of external loads. Such a function is expected to play a more important role in practical application scenarios where this actuator is utilized.

E. Demonstration of Stiffness Variation via Pressure-Input Shutdown

Lastly, this experiment was conducted to demonstrate the high responsiveness of the FASLJM from a control perspective. In the experiment, a vacuum pressure of 50 kPa was applied, and actuation of the FASLJM and the PLA–Sandpaper

Fig. 11. Experimental results of Section IV-E. A vacuum pressure of 50 kPa was applied, and the torque decay of the baseline-design (t1.3, D20) FASLJM and the PLA–sandpaper single-material-surface LJM is shown when the vacuum pressure supplied by the regulator was shut down to zero at the moment the applied torque reached 1.3 N·m. The actuators were driven at angular velocities of (a) $\omega = 0.04$ rad/s and (b) $\omega = 0.2$ rad/s. Each experiment was repeated three times, and the range and mean values of the measured data are presented. Based on the mean results, the residual torque was determined as a constant value obtained by a least-squares fit over the time intervals of (a) $t = [3 \text{ s}, 10 \text{ s}]$ and (b) $t = [1.4 \text{ s}, 2.2 \text{ s}]$.

Single-Material-Surface LJM was initiated in the same manner as in the previous section. When the external load applied by the testing machine reached 1.3 N·m, the power supply of the DC power source that provides the signal voltage to the vacuum pressure regulator was shut down, forcing the vacuum pressure supplied by the regulator to drop to zero while the actuation was continued. The experiments were performed while varying the angular velocity of actuation. Figure 11a shows the results obtained under a relatively low actuation speed of $\omega = 0.04$ rad/s, whereas Fig. 11b presents the results under a relatively high actuation speed of $\omega = 0.2$ rad/s. For each model, the experiment was repeated three times, and the range and mean values are reported. Each figure plots the torque applied by the actuator immediately after shutdown as a function of time. To quantify the residual torque that remains constant without decaying after shutdown, a constant value with a least-squares fit was applied to the mean torque data over the time window of 3–10 s in Fig. 11a and 1.4–2.2 s in Fig. 11b, based on the fitted curves.

As a result, in the low-angular-velocity experiments, the Single Material Surface LJM exhibited a residual torque of $\tau_{\text{residual}} = 0.0452$ N·m, whereas the FASLJM showed $\tau_{\text{residual}} = 0.0175$ N·m, confirming that the FASLJM yields approximately 2.6 times lower residual torque. In the high-angular-velocity experiments, the Single-Material-Surface LJM exhibited $\tau_{\text{residual}} = 0.0891$ N·m, while the FASLJM showed $\tau_{\text{residual}} = 0.0434$ N·m, indicating that the residual torque of the FASLJM is approximately 2.1 times lower.

It is considered that some of the residual torque values, particularly those observed for the FASLJM, arise from errors caused by factors external to the actuator, such as the inherent stiffness of the pneumatic pouch and friction generated in the experimental setup. Accordingly, it is expected that actuators exhibiting a larger pressure-induced stiffness increase—such as those with high-friction surfaces, a greater number of layers, or larger contact areas—would benefit more significantly from the introduction of the FASLJM in terms of residual torque

reduction. In addition, due to limitations in the actuation speed of the testing machine, the high angular velocity was set to 0.2 rad/s. In practical situations where external loads are applied by humans or other actuators, both the actuation speed and the pressure modulation speed can be substantially higher; therefore, the benefits of introducing the FASLJM are expected to be even more pronounced than those observed in the present experimental results. Lastly, in the present experiment, only a 2.6 m long straight 6×4 mm air tube was installed between the regulator output and the actuator input. In practical situations where more complex and bulky pneumatic systems are present, the effects observed in this experiment are expected to become even more pronounced.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we designed a Frictional Area-Separating Layer Jamming Mechanism (FASLJM) to mechanically address residual stiffness, which is a fundamental limitation of conventional LJMs. By inserting a porous polymer layer beneath a low-friction annular surface, contact between the high-friction surfaces is mechanically restricted in the low-pressure regime due to the stiffness of the porous polymer. Once the pressure exceeds a critical threshold, contact between the high-friction surfaces is established, resulting in an abrupt increase in stiffness. Through this mechanism, the stiffness in the low-pressure regime—where residual stiffness is most problematic—is effectively filtered.

For modeling the proposed actuator, the compressive properties of the porous polymer specimens were first characterized through compression tests, from which the critical pressure corresponding to each actuator design was determined. In addition, friction coefficients for each surface were identified through actuation tests using single-surface LJM configurations. Based on a free-body-diagram analysis, a two-stage analytical model was developed by separately accounting for the normal forces acting on each surface. This model was used to calculate the slopes of the pressure–slipping-torque relationships in both the subcritical and supercritical pressure regimes of the FASLJM. By varying the design parameters, it was confirmed that the proposed model follows the experimental data in a meaningful manner.

Finally, through experimental demonstrations, we showed that the FASLJM exhibits characteristics that are less dependent on external loads than those of a conventional LJM, and that it responds more effectively to abrupt pressure changes from high vacuum to atmospheric pressure, resulting in lower residual torque. Specifically, the FASLJM exhibited approximately 2.6 times lower residual torque at low actuation speeds (0.04 rad/s) and approximately 2.1 times lower residual torque at high actuation speeds (0.2 rad/s). These results suggest that, in practical situations involving rapid pressure modulation, high actuation speeds, and more complex pneumatic systems characterized by low flow conductance, the FASLJM can provide enhanced responsiveness and improved actuation accuracy.

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